

THE RELATIONSHIP OF LEADERSHIP STYLE WITH INDIVIDUALIZED EDUCATION PLANNING THROUGH THE LENS OF STRUCTURE FOR COLLABORATION IN SPECIAL EDUCATION OF PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This research explores how transformational leadership and instructional leadership, collaborative configurations, and implementing Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) operate in inclusive Khyber Pakhtunkhwa schools of Pakistan. By using a quantitative approach, quantitative data was obtained from 178 school administrators on a standardized questionnaire. The outcomes indicate that transformational leadership as well as instructional leadership both exhibit strong positive correlations with the implementation of IEPs, though collaborative configurations functioned as a mediator. Transformational leadership promotes participation and cooperation, while instructional leadership promotes goal alignment with education, both directly impacting IEP practice. Shared frameworks are essential in developing stakeholder involvement and joint decision-making, also improving IEP outcomes. Demographic differences identify differences in perceptions and practices of leadership through age, gender, designation, and sector, calling for adaptive leadership training and policy responses. Implications of the research highlight the critical role of sound leadership and interagency collaboration to break down institutional barriers to inclusive education. Areas of limitation for this research are geographic reach and use of self-reported data and, therefore, future research in other regions using other factors associated with IEP implementation is a recommendation. Research findings offer recommendations for policymakers and educators seeking to establish equitable, inclusive learning opportunities.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, Instructional leadership, Individualized education planning, Collaboration, Inclusive education.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a pillar of social progress, empowering people to live productive lives and make positive contributions to society. It is an effective tool for advancing economic progress, lessening disparity, and building social harmony. Nevertheless, the delivery of just and fair education, especially for children with special needs, is still a major issue in much of the world, including Pakistan. Special

education in Pakistan continues to be its early stages, with most schools, especially in rural regions, not having the infrastructure, trained staff, and resources to deliver inclusive education practices effectively (Neveset al., 2023). This capacity deficit perpetuates inequalities, keeping students with disabilities underserved and excluded from mainstream educational

opportunities. The Individualized Education Plan (IEP) is a potential vehicle to bridge such gaps. Widely hailed as the cornerstone of inclusive education, the IEP is a widely accepted framework designed to address the special needs of students with disabilities by adapting educational approaches to their unique needs. Despite its huge potential, the implementation of IEPs in Pakistan faces various impediments. The lack of adequate financial and material resources, a shortage of adequately qualified teachers, and strong ingrained societal orientations dismissing disability all face the widespread utilization of IEPs (Leithwood et al., 2008). These organizational barriers highlight the imperative need for an effective plan to overcome these issues and construct an inclusive educational environment. An IEP is not a paper; it's a collaborative effort to create the academic and social growth of disabled pupils. It sets specific individual learning objectives, teaching strategies, and accommodations, developed through collaboration between teachers, parents, professionals, and even students themselves. It ensures that each plan is made to meet the individual needs of the student, promoting not just academic achievement but social integration (Sánchez et al., 2019). Advantages of IEPs on paper are well chronicled, though, but achieving that depends upon the interaction among numerous key determinants, for instance, the leadership styles as well as construction of collaborative settings (Lambrecht et al., 2022).

Educational leadership plays an important role in determining the effectiveness of inclusive practices. Transformational leadership, wherein the emphasis is on inspiring and motivating workers towards a shared vision, is particularly effective in building an inclusive culture. Transformational leadership has been shown to enhance teacher motivation, stimulate innovation, and create an environment in which the teachers feel empowered to take up and implement inclusive practices, including the development and implementation of IEPs (Bass, 1985; Lambrecht et al., 2022). Instructional leadership, which is centered on school teaching and learning's core purpose—prioritizes improving pedagogical quality, aligning instructional plans with students' needs, and supporting teachers to effectively apply educational targets (Leithwood et al., 2004). These two leadership styles are complementary in shaping the conditions necessary for effective IEP

implementation. The establishment of collaborative frameworks is also necessary in the effective application of IEPs. Those kinds of frameworks enable multiple stakeholders—teachers, parents, experts, and administrators—to assume active roles in developing and implementing plans that address the varied needs of students with disabilities. Robust collaborative frameworks facilitate the sharing of resources, continuous professional growth, and participatory decision-making, promoting an environment conducive to effective IEP implementation (Adams et al., 2018; Sánchez et al., 2019). There is existing research that shows schools with robust collaborative structures are best able to focus on the individualized student needs, eventually attaining higher learning outcomes (Cavendish & Connor, 2018). Even with these findings, Pakistan's case has special challenges of its own. The Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) province, for instance, is plagued with chronic resource shortages, cultural resistance to change, and inadequate professional development of teachers (Neves et al., 2023). These obstacles not only hinder the enforcement of IEPs but also worsen the broader issue of systemic exclusion of students with disabilities. Although Pakistan is a signatory to global instruments such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) and has committed itself to Sustainable Development Goal 4, which talks of inclusive and equitable quality education, progress remains slow. Insufficient policy guidance, framework for accountability, and steady funding compound these factors even more, projecting the urgencies for interventions with a strategy (Sánchez et al., 2019).

This study aims to investigate the intricate connection between instructional and transformational leadership styles and the implementation of IEPs, with specific focus on the mediating role of collaborative structures. Recent studies have highlighted the direct and indirect pathways by which leadership styles affect the implementation of IEPs. Transformational leadership is likely to work indirectly by establishing cooperative frameworks, while instructional leadership has direct and mediated effects on IEP outcomes (Lambrecht et al., 2022). By exploring these processes within the context of KP's special education department, this research seeks to provide prescribable recommendations for

improving inclusive schooling practice in Pakistan. Specifically, it investigates how leadership impacts the development and functioning of collaborative frameworks and how these facilitate effective implementation of IEP. The findings of this study have potential to impact policy and practice, establishing evidence-based strategies for overcoming system barriers to inclusion and ensuring that every student, regardless of their ability, is offered quality education (Lambrecht et al., 2022; Neves et al., 2023).

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Leadership Styles in Educational Settings

Inclusive education is a philosophy based on the belief that all children should be taught in regular classrooms regardless of their disabilities or abilities so as to have equal learning opportunities. It is therefore aimed at the acceptance of differences, equity, and accessibility and is established through global policies such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, 2006). This method's essence is the implementation of Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) that are generally applied as a basis to assist children with special educational needs (SEN). IEPs are a written individualized plan for the students where they get to be informed of their learning objectives and the teaching methods and materials used to reach the students' potential needs. The participatory nature of the IEP development process is its key to achieving the desired results, and this can be achieved through the help of the participatory process that involves educators, parents, specialists, and, sometimes, students themselves (Sánchez et al., 2019). In practice, the concept of IEPs as a tool to encourage inclusive practices may be appealing; however, emphatic arguments about the existence of IEPs in schools are often annulled by such obstacles as the lack of resources, professionally trained teachers, and the absence of the willingness to adopt changes (Mitchell, Morton, & Hornby, 2010). For instance, Cavendish and Connor (2018) exposed how negative collaboration from the stakeholders might hinder IEPs to bring about a significant realization in the learning process. In the context of Pakistan, inclusive education is everywhere a new reality where the huge disparities between rural and urban

populations have very limited access and quality to education. Special schools' attainability and quality are most of the time the two main factors that limit accessibility, not to mention the fact that teacher training is inadequate and disabled people have no access to their rights (Neves et al., 2023).

Leadership style in Education Setting

Two prominent leadership styles transformational and instructional—have been extensively studied for their impact on educational outcomes and inclusive practices.

Transformational Leadership:

Transformational leadership focuses on inspiring and motivating employees toward a common vision. Leaders with this type of style place a high value on creating trust, the development of the professionals, and stimulating innovation. Transformational leadership has been used in inclusive education and found to generate an inclusion culture because it encourages teamwork and enables teachers to meet the various needs of students (Bass, 1985; Ainscow & Sandill, 2010). Lambrecht et al. (2022) have established through their research that transformational leaders have a crucial role in the development of collaborative frameworks, which are required for effective IEP implementation.

Transformational leadership also facilitates social cohesion in schools, allowing people with different backgrounds to collaborate harmoniously. By acknowledging and meeting the unique strengths of their workforce, transformational leaders foster an appreciative climate in which teachers are highly valued and encouraged to participate in collaborative processes (Robinson et al., 2008). Yet its effects on educational outcomes tend to be indirect and mediated by the development of supportive structures and a positive school culture (Gumus, Bulut, & Bellibas, 2013).

Instructional Leadership:

Instructional leadership focuses on the core mission of schools: teaching and learning. Leaders with this focus set pedagogic quality as its priority, bring instructional strategies in line with the educational goals, and assist the teachers with their professional development as well as through performance monitoring (Leithwood et al., 2008). Instructional leadership, on the other hand, in an inclusive education model directly impacts IEP

quality and consistency by supporting teaching practices which are tailored for the specific requirements of students having disabilities (Goddard et al., 2015).

Collaborative Structures as a Mediating Factor

By definition, collaborative structures include the systematic and unsystematic forms that promote IEP development and its implementation by the cooperation of several stakeholders – parents, teachers, specialists, and administrators. Collaborative structures are of utmost importance in that they are able to ensure decision making, financial resources allocation, and continuous professional education are happening at the same time. (Adams et al., 2018; Cavendish & Connor, 2018)

Studies have pointed out that the role of leadership in the creation and maintenance of collaborative structures is crucial. Transformational leadership allows an informal interaction between different groups of people while instructional leadership confirms that the collaborative activities they engage in are within the educational goals and teaching methods (Honingh & Hooge, 2014). Lambrecht et al. (2022) indicated, for instance, that transformational leadership reinforces the IEP implementation process through the creation of

collaborative structures i.e., it works indirectly. Instructional leadership, on the other hand, not only had direct effects, but the indirect effects were also observed.

Overseas works have shown in many instances that cooperation is one of the most effective ways to carry out IEPs. Mitchell, Morton, and Hornby (2010) discovered this fact while conducting a survey on more than 190 IEP studies across countries and found that mutual support was the key to success. Nilsen (2017) found that IEP processes in collaboration had a positive impact on the quality of the education plan, and also that students' academic and social outcomes would increase among students with disabilities.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework for this study is grounded in the relationship between leadership styles, collaborative structures, and the implementation of Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) in inclusive education settings. It integrates theories of transformational and instructional leadership with empirical insights on collaborative frameworks, illustrating their combined impact on the successful implementation of IEPs in the context of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), Pakistan.

FIGURE 1
Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research adopts a quantitative design to systematically evaluate the relationships among the

study's variables. Quantitative methods are well-suited for statistically analyzing data and drawing

general conclusions. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from school leaders, including principals, vice principals, and coordinators in public and private sector inclusive schools across KPK. This design enables the study to capture diverse perspectives across various school contexts and demographic settings.

Population and Sample

The target population for this study includes 330 school leaders (principals, vice principals, and coordinators) from inclusive schools across KPK.

Sampling Technique: Convenience sampling was used on account of the time constraints and resources available. This form of non-probability sampling allowed for quick and efficient data collection by targeting subjects available and willing to participate. Although this method narrows generalizability with respect to results, it

offers practical insights in leadership and collaboration in KPK schools.

Sample Size: The study surveyed 178 school leaders, determined using Cochran's formula at a confidence level of 95 percent and margin error of 5 percent. Thus, the sample size guarantees very wide representation across different contexts of schools including urban and rural areas and public and private sectors.

Data Collection Instruments

A structured questionnaire was designed to measure key variables in the study. The questionnaire consisted of three main sections:

Variables, Dimensions, and Measurement

The study examined four key variables, measured using validated scales adapted from previous studies.

Table 1 provides an overview of these variables.

Variables	Components	No of Items	Source
Transformational Leadership	Creating a trustworthy atmosphere, fostering open and cooperative social relations	8	(PISA, Ramm et al., 2006)
Instructional Leadership	Using student assessment results, developing educational goals, coordinating teaching programs	8	(PISA, Hertel et al., 2014)
Structures for Collaboration	Time for collaboration, integration in the regular school day	4	(Lambrecht et al., 2022).
Implementation of IEP	Dynamic and adaptable learning goals, involvement of multi-professional teams, students, and parents	11	LISUM (2010)

The online questionnaire was used to assess the following variables. Transformational leadership was assessed using the human resources scale from the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA, Ramm et al. 2006). The scale consisted of N = 8 items (e.g. I create a trustworthy atmosphere by fostering open and cooperative social relations. Instructional leadership was assessed following the scale used in PISA 2009 (Hertel et al. 2014). The adapted scale consisted of N = 8 items (e.g. I use students' assessment results to develop the school's educational goals.) and was reliable. Structural conditions for collaboration were assessed using N = 4 items (e.g. Time for collaboration, for example

for lesson planning and meetings, is a regular part of working time and is integrated in the regular school day.) Implementation of IEP was assessed using a scale consisting of N = 11 items. It was developed within the framework of the research project. The items were developed in relation to the recommendations given by LISUM (2010). Individualized education planning has 11 items.

Data Analysis

To run the tests and review the data collected through surveys, "IBM SPSS Statistics 25" are used. To ascertain how closely the independent variable

and dependent variable are connected, as well as to as certain how much variation in the independent variable is responsible for the change in the dependent variable, correlation and regression analyses are performed on the collected data.

Below is a list of the tests that were performed:

- Descriptive Statistics
- Reliability Analysis
- Demographic Analysis

- Correlation Analysis
- Regression Analysis

Research Technique

To analyze the hypotheses Descriptive Statistics and Mediation model 04 of Hayes [2013] PROCESS macro regression-based approach has been used by using SPSS package.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
TL	178	3.93375	.48137
IL	178	3.05875	.31439
SC	178	2.69250	.51583
IP	178	3.78545	.40945

The descriptive statistics for the key variables in this study provide insight into respondents' perceptions of transformational leadership (TL), instructional leadership (IL), collaborative structures (SC), and IEP implementation (IP). The mean score for transformational leadership (M = 3.93, SD = 0.48) suggests that school leaders in inclusive schools exhibit moderately high levels of behaviors associated with inspiring and motivating their staff to achieve shared goals. This indicates a positive inclination toward fostering trust, collaboration, and an inclusive school culture.

Instructional leadership (M = 3.05, SD = 0.31) was rated slightly lower, reflecting moderate levels of practices such as using student assessment data, aligning teaching strategies with IEP objectives, and supporting teacher development. This comparatively lower score highlights an area where more targeted efforts could enhance the effectiveness of IEP implementation. Collaborative structures (M = 2.69, SD = 0.52) received the lowest mean score, indicating that systems enabling teamwork, such as scheduling time for collaboration and integrating teamwork into daily school operations, are underdeveloped in many schools. This finding underscores the need to strengthen collaborative frameworks to ensure a cohesive approach to inclusive education. Finally, IEP implementation (M = 3.79, SD = 0.41) was rated relatively high, suggesting that schools are moderately successful in implementing IEPs,

including involving multi-professional teams and tailoring learning goals to students' needs. However, the variability in responses, as indicated by the standard deviation, points to inconsistencies in implementation across schools.

The Table displays the mean score compares in the four aspects, the Transformational Leadership, Instructional Leadership, Structure for Collaboration, and the Individualized Education Planning by demographic variables including the gender, age, their position, years of experience and sector. For gender, all factors have a slightly higher mean score among males than among females, so it can be inferred that male participants perceived or were aligned with leadership and education planning factors more than female participants.

Overall, the mean results are highest for the age groups 41 to 45 years for all the factors analyzed, which implies that the leadership and collaboration structures are better perceived in this age bracket. Nevertheless, overall, respondents within the 45 years old and above category tend to have lower scores, Individualized Education Planning refers to different experiences or expectations due to age.

As in table, Vice Principals record the highest mean scores in all factors, although the difference in the means is not incredibly significant. Structure for Collaboration and Individualized Education Planning reveal that Vice Principals have a stronger emphasis or higher perceptions of how effective they are in implementing and meeting

requirements in the two factor areas compared to Coordinators and Principals. Finally, as for the differences in the mean scores for each factor it can be stated that coordinators have the lowest mean scores across most of the factors, which may indicate that the differences in the role of employees and their responsibilities affect their attitudes.

When it comes to experiencing those with 4-6 years' experience, we can see that the scores in Instruction Leadership and Structures for collaboration are higher, which might indicate that experience bracket is more related to the discussed factors. As for years of experience, individuals with 13 years or more experience reveal the smallest scores, perhaps, due to exhaustion or having different values at work nowadays.

In determining the responses, the public sector respondents received a higher mean score on all factors than the private sector respondents particularly in Structures for Collaboration and Individual Education Plan. This suggests that public sector professionals might compare structures of collaboration to planning with employees in the private sector.

Overall, the data highlights some variations with regards to specific demographic parameters based on the general trends which show that perceptions of leadership and collaboration are conditioned with age, designation, experience and sector, preferences. Such findings may help to develop strategies for improving leadership performance and cooperation in particular sets of people.

Reliability of Research Instrument

Reliability analysis is used to check the consistency and reliability of the questionnaire, as measured by Cronbach's alpha. A scale is considered reliable when the alpha value exceeds 0.60 (Santos, 1999). The reliability of independent variables, transformational leadership and instructional leadership is 0.704 and 0.702, respectively. The reliability of collaborative structures and IEP implementation is 0.721 and 0.704, respectively. The overall reliability of the questionnaire, which combines all 31 items, is 0.818, indicating excellent internal consistency and acceptability for measuring the study variables.

Correlation testing

Correlations	TL	IL	SC	IP
TL	1			
IL	.652**	1		
SC	.485**	.488**	1	
IP	.634**	.634**	.515**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation table shows that there are a number of social relationships among the considered variables. TL is positively and significantly correlated to IL in the study where 'r' = 0.652, $p < 0.01$, proving that the more TL increases the more IL increases as well. Further, there are moderate positive correlations between TL and Structures for Collaboration (SC) $t(128) = 7.953$, $p < 0.01$, $r = .485$ and between TL and Individualized Education Planning (IP) $t(128) = 11.792$, $p < 0.01$, $r = .634$ which infers that TL has positive relation both with structural collaboration as well as with individualized planning.

Instructional Leadership (IL) correlates positively with SC with a coefficient of .488 ($p < 0.01$) and has a high positive correlation with an IP with the coefficient of .634 ($p < 0.01$); Hence, higher levels

of IL underpin better collaboration and planning processes. In addition, SC has a positive relationship with IP with a correlation coefficient of 0.515 and $p < 0.01$, this finding implies that effective collaboration structures promote the enhancement of IE planning among teachers. All variables are 2-tailed, and at 0.01 level of significance, the findings indicate strongly related leadership styles, collaborative structures, and education planning practices.

Hypothesis Testing

To analyze the hypotheses Mediation model 14 of Hayes [2013] PROCESS macro regression-based approach has been used by using SPSS package.

H1: Transformational leadership has a positive relationship with Implementation of IEP.

Variable	β	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
TL	.7230	.0914	7.9078	.0000	.5425	.9034

The study established a strong positive relationship between transformational leadership and IEP implementation. A β of 0.7230 indicates that for every one-unit increase in transformational leadership, IEP implementation improves by 0.7230 units, reflecting a substantial impact. The relationship is statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($p = 0.0000$), ruling out the possibility of random effects. The t -value of 7.9078 further confirms the strength and reliability of this relationship.

The 95% confidence interval (0.5425 to 0.9034) does not include zero, providing high confidence in the positive nature of this association. The standardized β reflects a 72.3% improvement in IEP implementation for every one-unit change in transformational leadership, controlling for other variables. These findings support the hypothesis of a positive correlation between transformational leadership and IEPs, emphasizing the transformative role of leadership in enhancing IEP practices.

H2: Instructional leadership has a positive relationship with Implementation of IEP.

Variable	β	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
IT	.7209	.0915	7.8784	.0000	.5403	.9015

According to the analysis it emerged that there was positive correlation between instructional leadership and the practice of IEPA. The coefficient $\beta=0.7209$ shows the large impact since for every one-unit increase in instructional leadership, there is a corresponding increase of 0.7209 units of IEP implementation. This association turns out to be highly significant at $p < 0.0000$ which indicates that the impact observed is not at all friendly samples or in other words it lacks chance factors. This positive relationship is further backed by a moderately high t -value of 7.8784.

The 95% confidence interval estimated at 0.5403 and 0.9015 excludes zero thereby giving credible evidence of the positive relationship. The obtained value of $\beta = .7209$ suggest that there was a significant effect size, implying that a one-unit improvement in instructional leadership would result in about 72.1% improvement in the implementation of IEPs provided the other

conditions remain constitutional leadership, there is an associated increase of 0.7209 units in IEP implementation, signifying a substantial impact. This relationship is highly statistically significant, as reflected by the p -value of 0.0000, which confirms that the observed effect is not due to chance. The t -value of 7.8784 further underscores the strength and reliability of this positive relationship.

The 95% confidence interval, with lower and upper bounds of 0.5403 and 0.9015 respectively, does not include zero, providing robust evidence of the positive association. The magnitude of $\beta=0.7209$ indicates a significant effect size, suggesting that a one-unit increase in instructional leadership would lead to approximately a 72.1% improvement in IEP implementation, assuming other factors remain constant.

H3: Transformational leadership has a positive relationship with collaborative structures.

Variable	β	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
TL	.2988	.0406	7.3527	.0000	.2186	.3790

Consequently, the levels of transformational leadership positively correlate with collaborative structures. The obtained coefficient of $\beta=0.2988$ means that increase of transformational leadership by one point is followed by increase of the development of collaborated structures by 0.2988 points, therefore, the effect is positive and moderate. Responding increase of 0.2988 units in the development of collaborative structures, demonstrating a moderate positive effect. The relationship in the analysis is also statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.0000, which means that is highly unlikely that achievement happened purely by chance. Other evidence for this relationship is also the high t-value of 7.3527.

The 95% confidence interval by log odds is from 0.2186 to 0.3790 does not include zero further supporting the positive association. Thus, the obtained moderate effect size means that engaged

leadership embraces crucial importance for building collaborative structures, but the impact is not as strong as in other circumstances, there is a corresponding increase of 0.2988 units in the development of collaborative structures, demonstrating a moderate positive effect. This relationship is statistically significant, as evidenced by the p-value of 0.0000, confirming that the observed effect is unlikely to occur by chance. The t-value of 7.3527 further supports the robustness of this relationship.

The 95% confidence interval, ranging from 0.2186 to 0.3790, does not include zero, providing additional assurance of the positive association. The moderate effect size represented by $\beta=0.2988$ suggests that transformational leadership plays an important role in fostering collaborative structures, though the influence is not as pronounced as in other contexts.

H4: Instructional leadership has a positive relationship with collaborative structures.

Variable	β	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
IL	.3001	.0405	7.4139	.0000	.2202	.3799

The analysis also reveals a positive direct correlation between instructional leadership and collaborative structures. The value of $\beta = 0.3001$ proves that with each one-unit increase in instructional leadership, there is a corresponding 0.3001 unit change in collaborative structures signifying a positive moderate effect. Thus, there is an associated increase of 0.3001 units in collaborative structures, reflecting a moderate positive effect. The relationship is also significant, given by the p-value of 0.0000, which rules out chance as a factor in deriving the findings. The t-Test shows that the value of $t = 7.4139$ and so it enforces the fact the relationship found is strong and very dependable. The 95% confidence interval

obtained is 0.2202 and 0.3799 and does not encompass zero indicating the positive nature of the relationship. The data evidence indicates a moderate, positive effect size ($\beta=0.3001$), which implies that instructional leadership is an important antecedent of functional collaborative structures in organizations.

These analyses indicate that the hypothesis that there is a positive correlation between instructional leadership and collaborative structures is a sound assumption. This goes a long way in supporting the view that instructional leadership entails fostering environments that support collaboration, effective teamwork in the actualization of goals and objectives.

H5: There is a positive relationship between structures for collaboration with Implementation of IEP.

Variable	β	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
SC	.6308	.1488	4.2402	.0000	.3372	.9244

The analysis indicates a strong positive correlation between collaborative structures and IEP implementation ($\beta = 0.6308$), demonstrating that a one-unit increase in collaborative structures leads

to a 0.6308-unit increase in IEP implementation. This substantial effect is statistically significant ($p = 0.0000$), ruling out the possibility of random

chance. The relationship's reliability is further supported by a t-value of 4.2402.

The 95% confidence interval (0.3372 to 0.9244) excludes zero, confirming the positive nature of the relationship. The significant effect size ($\beta = 0.6308$) highlights the crucial role of collaborative structures in enhancing IEP implementation.

These findings validate the hypothesis that collaborative structures positively influence IEP practices, emphasizing the importance of fostering collaboration to ensure effective individualized educational plans.

H6: Structures for collaboration mediates the relationship of Transformational leadership and Implementation of IEP

Direct effect of Transformational leadership on Implementation of IEP					
Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.7230	.0914	7.9078	.0000	.5425	.9034
Indirect effect(s) of Transformational leadership on Implementation of IEP					
	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI	
	.1894	.0481	.1010	.2921	

The analysis confirms that transformational leadership significantly influences IEP implementation both directly ($\beta = 0.7230$, $t = 7.9078$, $p = 0.0000$, CI: 0.5425 to 0.9034) and indirectly through collaborative structures. The indirect effect (0.1894, SE = 0.0481, CI: 0.1010 to 0.2921) underscores the mediating role of collaborative structures, which channel the impact

of transformational leadership on IEPs. These findings validate the hypothesis that collaborative structures partially mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and IEP implementation, emphasizing the combined importance of leadership and collaboration in effective IEP delivery.

H7: Structures for collaboration mediate the relationship of Instructional leadership and Implementation of IEP.

Direct effect of Instructional leadership on Implementation of IEP					
Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.7209	.0915	7.8784	.0000	.5403	.9015
Indirect effect(s) of Instructional leadership on Implementation of IEP					
	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI	
	.1893	.0470	.1045	.2880	

The study confirms that instructional leadership significantly influences IEP implementation directly ($\beta = 0.7209$, $t = 7.8784$, $p = 0.0000$, CI: 0.5403 to 0.9015) and indirectly through collaborative structures. A mediating relationship emerges between collaborative structures and instructional leadership effects on IEP delivery

according to the indirect effect value ($\beta = 0.1893$, BootSE = 0.0470, CI: 0.1045 to 0.2880). The research shows that collaborative structures play a partial mediating role between instructional leadership and IEP delivery. The need for collaborative practices and instructional leadership

remains vital to succeed in implementing IEPs for students with disabilities.

Conclusion

The study reveals how transformational and instructional leadership alongside collaborative structures function as key elements for implementing Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) effectively in inclusive schools within Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Direct influences of leadership styles appeared as major factors in IEP implementation while collaborative structures functioned as the central mediator. The combination of transformational leadership with instructional leadership fosters inclusion through collaboration while maintaining educational goal alignment. Stakeholder participation and joint decision-making processes in collaborative systems boost IEP implementation outcomes. The study shows that public sector schools implement greater collaboration which provides valuable insight for enhancing private sector educational settings.

Implication

The research paper focuses on transformational and instructional leadership as key elements that lead to successful implementation of IEPs to establish inclusive education. The research paper highlights that collaborative structures between leadership roles enable effective leadership effects while proposing practical strategies to enhance training programs along with policy guidelines and resource allocation for inclusive practices. The findings enable policymakers and educators to develop equitable learning spaces which effectively address the requirements of diverse student populations.

Limitations and Future Directions

Limitations

This research is geographically confined to Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, which can limit the generalizability of its results to other contexts. The use of self-reported information could lead to social desirability bias, and convenience sampling restricts the sample's representativeness. The study also concentrates on leadership styles and working relationships, which might not capture other determinant variables.

Future Directions

Future studies can extend to other areas and utilize a more representative sample to increase generalization. The use of mixed methods, e.g., qualitative interviews and quantitative questionnaires, might give richer information. Future research should also investigate other leadership behaviors, cultural aspects, and other mediators or moderators that affect IEP implementation to extend the knowledge regarding inclusive education practices.

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